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Skills4EOSC Quality Compass App

Improving your Open Science training course

Skills4EOSC Quality Compass App

Improving your Open Science training course

Version 1.0 (August 2025)

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Disclaimer

This booklet was produced by Skills4EOSC, a project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140].

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DOI link

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16748616>

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1. Introduction to the S4E Quality Assurance Framework (QAF)

WHAT IS THE QAF?

The S4E Quality Assurance Framework (QAF) is a practical, community-endorsed reference that helps improve the quality of Open Science training courses. It's not a rigid standard but a set of flexible guidelines and best practices to help course creators make sure their learning materials are clear, FAIR and aligned with good practices.

WHY IS IT IMPORTANT?

The S4E QAF promotes best practices and self-evaluation tools to ensure coherence between content and container: a course about Open Science should also embed Open Science principles in how it's designed, presented, and shared.

WHO IS IT FOR?

This framework is designed for a wide range of users:

- **Trainers and course designers** creating or updating learning materials in Open Science
- **Instructional coordinators** planning Open Science training and managing delivery platforms
- **S4E Competence Centers** designing Open Science courses

You don't need to be an expert in FAIR, legal or technical aspects — the QAF supports everyone with user-friendly steps and tools.

WHAT KIND OF MATERIALS DOES IT FOCUS ON?

The QAF is designed to assess complete training courses, rather than individual learning objects or small resources. It applies to online, in-person, and hybrid formats, focusing on quality at the course level.

| HOW DOES THE QAF WORK?

The QAF is structured around four key areas, called **sub-frameworks**:

- **Essential**: addressing core elements like goals, target audience, content structure
- **Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS)**: making sure the course builds on key skills in Open Science audience for the correspondent audience
- **FAIR-by-Design**: ensuring materials are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
- **ELSI (Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues)**: handling licenses, data protection, and ethics

Each of these areas includes indicators — clear Yes/No questions that help check course quality. In some cases, indicators also offer a third option, “Not applicable”, when the criterion doesn’t apply to a given course.

| WHAT ARE LEVELS OF COMPLIANCE?

Indicators are grouped into two levels:

- **Minimal compliance**: the core recommendations for a good quality course
- **Detailed compliance**: advanced practices that go beyond the basics

| WHAT ARE MATURITY LEVELS?

Maturity levels help users grow their use of the QAF over time. They establish a path for continuous improvement that ranges from:

- **Initial** (no formal QA process)
- **Defined** (some minimal indicators used)
- **Managed** (full minimal compliance + quality review)
- **Optimized** (detailed compliance + full minimal compliance + continuous improvement)

By understanding where you stand, you can plan realistic improvements and celebrate progress!

QAF STRUCTURE

The framework has a total of 51 indicators. You can see how they are distributed in the following tables by sub-framework and by section.

TABLE BY SUB-FRAMEWORK

DISTRIBUTION OF INDICATORS BY SUB-FRAMEWORK									
NUMBER OF INDICATORS		ESSENTIAL COMPLIANCE		FAIR COMPLIANCE		MVS COMPLIANCE		ELSI COMPLIANCE	
TOTAL	51	TOTAL	20	TOTAL	17	TOTAL	7	TOTAL	7
MINIMAL	28	MINIMAL	11	MINIMAL	8	MINIMAL	4	MINIMAL	5
DETAILED	23	DETAILED	9	DETAILED	9	DETAILED	3	DETAILED	2

TABLE BY SECTION

DISTRIBUTION OF INDICATORS BY SECTION									
NUMBER OF INDICATORS		CONTENT & STRUCTURE		IMPLEMENTATION		EVALUATION		LICENSING & ETHICS	
TOTAL	51	TOTAL	20	TOTAL	16	TOTAL	7	TOTAL	8
MINIMAL	28	MINIMAL	15	MINIMAL	7	MINIMAL	0	MINIMAL	6
DETAILED	23	DETAILED	5	DETAILED	9	DETAILED	7	DETAILED	2

2. QAF Tools by Stage of Course Design: the Checklist & Guide and the App

To make the QAF easy and practical to use, two key tools were developed to support different stages of your course design process:

2.1 During Course Design – The QAF Checklist & Guide

When you're in the early stages of creating or redesigning a course, the [QAF Checklist & Guide](#) is your go-to tool. It helps you plan ahead and keep track of what matters most for delivering a high-quality Open Science learning experience. It's also a simple way to get familiar with the QAF and how quality review works – without feeling overwhelmed.

WHAT IS IT?

An interactive online checklist that guides you through the QAF indicators in a clear, user-friendly format.

WHAT DOES IT INCLUDE?

- A short introduction to the framework, levels of compliance and maturity, and its sub-frameworks (first page)
- All indicators grouped by level (Minimal/Detailed) and sub-framework (pages 2 to 5)
- An extra section only for ELSI experts addressing the delivery learning platform (page 6)
- Clickable boxes for self-checking
- Help buttons with notes and best practices

HOW CAN YOU USE IT?

Use the checklist as a **planning tool**. Go through the questions while designing your course. It helps you:

- Remember important quality elements
- Organise content logically
- Ensure you're addressing ethical and legal, MVS, and FAIR-related aspects early on

Tip: Don't worry if you can't tick every box yet – the goal is to build awareness and prepare for improvement.

FAIR-BY-DESIGN SUB-FRAMEWORK

FAIR-by-design Sub-Framework

Main source: D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials

MINIMAL

DETAILED

NOTES	QUALITY INDICATOR	BEST PRACTICES	ANSWER		
?	At least one searchable repository has the complete learning resource (including instructors' info) deposited or indexed.	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Findable	Reusable
		Metadata is available to describe the resource	i		
?	Accessibility checker tool has been utilised to improve the accessibility of the learning resource	i	<input type="checkbox"/>	Accessible	Findable
?	Access rules (authentication and authorisation) are implemented	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
?	RDA minimal metadata is used for the learning resource	i	<input type="checkbox"/>	Reusable	Findable
?	Open file format agnosticism and of existing software	i	<input type="checkbox"/>		
?	Reused resource compliant with OAI-PMH	i	<input type="checkbox"/>	Findable	Reusable
?	Licenses define permissive terms or policy information that allow adaptations and derivations, making the learning resource reusable	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
	Feedback options are included, allowing users to provide comments for improvement	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Findable	Reusable
?	Open community approach is adopted by the resource to enhance its quality and reachability	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
?	Rating is available for the learning resource	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Findable	Reusable
?	Instructor kit is included in the learning resource (assessment, lesson plan, activities description and facilitation guide)	i	<input type="checkbox"/>		
?	Versioning system is employed to track and control changes in the materials	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Findable	Reusable
?	Logical units are defined around a minimum of one learning objective	i	<input type="checkbox"/>		
?	Learning experience quality has been evaluated by a third party	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Findable	Reusable
?	Controlled vocabularies (CVs) are used to describe the resource characteristics in alignment with the chosen metadata schema	i	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
?	Catalogue searchable in at least one relevant catalogue	i	<input type="checkbox"/>	Findable	Reusable

Permissive license is needed so that others can reuse the resource. Allowing adaptation / derivation enables wider reuse where the content can be changed and adapted to someone else's needs and purposes.

2.2 After Course Design - The S4E Quality Compass App

Once your course is ready — or nearly ready — you can move on to the [S4E Quality Compass app](#).

WHAT IS IT?

A free, open, and user-friendly web app that allows you to self-assess your course against the full QAF.

WHY USE IT?

- Check whether your course meets **Minimal** and **Detailed** compliance levels
- Get a detailed breakdown of your results
- Receive tailored **best practices** to improve your course
- Share results internally or with partners
- Provide feedback to the Skills4EOsc community and help refine the framework

IN SUMMARY

STAGE	TOOL	TOOL
During design	Checklist & Guide	Planning and structuring your course with quality in mind
After design	S4E Quality Compass	Self-assessing the course and improving based on results

Next up, we'll walk you through how the S4E Quality Compass works — step by step.

3. The S4E Quality Compass App: Overview, Walkthrough & Data Collection

The **S4E Quality Compass app** is designed to help you easily evaluate your course using the Quality Assurance Framework (QAF). It guides you through a structured self-assessment and provides immediate, actionable feedback.

WHAT IS IT?

A web-based tool that walks you through the QAF in a clear and easy-to-understand format.

WHO IS IT FOR?

- Trainers and course designers creating or finalizing an Open Science course
- Project partners and Competence Centers applying the QAF
- Anyone who wants to check and improve course quality using the Skills4EOSC approach

3.1. Navigating the App: Pages and Features

The app includes three main sections:

1. ABOUT PAGE

- A brief overview of the QAF, the app, and its purpose
- Introduction and links to key outputs such as the Checklist & Guide
- Supporting resources, including the MVS, FAIR-by-design methodology, and ELSI aspects

2. SELF-ASSESSMENT PAGE

- This is where the real work (and value!) happens
- The self-assessment is divided into five sections, one for background information, and four aligned with the QAF structure from a course design perspective

1. ABOUT PAGE

Skills4eosc S4E Quality Compass

Welcome!

Welcome to the Skills4EOSC Quality Compass, the app that helps you in making your courses compliant with the Skills4EOSC Quality Assurance Framework. In our mission of ensuring quality in the full life-cycle of training in Open Science, we have produced two main outputs that will guide you in taking your learning resources to the next level: the QA Checklist & Guide and the Skills4EOSC Quality Self-assessment Test.

By following our guidelines, you will ensure the integration of the FAIR-by-design methodology, the Minimum Viable Skillsets model, key Ethical and Legal aspects and other e-learning quality criteria in your Open Science course.

At which stage of designing your course are you?

First stage of designing your course
The S4E Quality Checklist & Guide

Last stage of designing your course
The S4E Quality Self-assessment Test

2. SELF-ASSESSMENT PAGE / CONTENT & STRUCTURE

SECTION	KEY AREAS	WHAT IT COVERS?
0. Background information	General information about you as a course designer	Your involvement in Skills4EOSC, your organisation, your role, your field, the title of your course, your prior experience in QA
Content & Structure	Metadata & Publication	Title
		Keywords
		Metadata
		Vocabularies
		Catalogue
		Repository
		Language
	Targets	Audience
		Expertise level
		Goal
		Objectives and outcomes
	Design	Program
Logical unit		
Learning style		

2. SELF-ASSESSMENT PAGE > IMPLEMENTATION

SECTION	KEY AREAS	WHAT IT COVERS?
0. Background information	General information about you as a course designer	Your involvement in Skills4EOSC, your organisation, your role, your field, the title of your course, your prior experience in QA
Implementation	Technical & Accessibility Aspects	Technology
		File formats
		Prerequisites
		Accessibility
	Delivery	Trainer
		Instructor kit
		Timescale
		Delivery
		Costs
		Access rules
	Co-creation	Reused resources
		Open community
		Versioning

2. SELF-ASSESSMENT PAGE > EVALUATION & LICENSING & ETHICS

SECTION	KEY AREAS	WHAT IT COVERS?
0. Background information	General information about you as a course designer	Your involvement in Skills4EOSC, your organisation, your role, your field, the title of your course, your prior experience in QA
Evaluation	Assessment	Activities
		Grading
		Course certification
	Guidance	Feedback
		Rating
		Learning experience quality
Licensing & Ethics	Terms of Service and Personal Data	ToS and personal data
	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)
	Ethics	Ethics Information

3. General Feedback

- Final questions about your experience using the QAF and its tools (Checklist & Guide and the app). This is your chance to provide feedback on any aspect from a general perspective.

The screenshot shows the 'S4E Quality Compass' app interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the Skills4EOSC logo and a hamburger menu icon. Below the header is a dark sidebar with icons for home, menu, search, and user profile. The main content area is orange and features the title 'General Feedback survey'. The text explains the project's goal to support high-quality, FAIR, and community-aligned learning materials for Open Science. It describes the Skills4EOSC Quality Assurance Framework (QAF) and mentions two tools: the Checklist & Guide and the S4E Quality Compass app. A call to action button at the bottom reads 'Start General Feedback Survey'. The footer contains copyright information and logos for Skills4EOSC, EOSC, the European Union, UC3M, and Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

General Feedback survey

One of the core goals of the Skills4EOSC project is to support the development of high-quality, FAIR, and community-aligned learning materials for Open Science. To do this, we created the Skills4EOSC Quality Assurance Framework (QAF)—a practical reference tool designed to guide trainers, course creators, and instructional designers through essential quality indicators for building and evaluating Open Science learning materials.

To make the framework more usable and adaptable, we've built two main tools:

- the Checklist & Guide for planning during the course design phase,
- and the S4E Quality Compass app, a self-assessment tool for reviewing completed materials.

As part of our commitment to continuous improvement, we are collecting feedback from real users like you. Your experience, opinions, and ideas are key to making the QAF even more effective, practical, and user-friendly.

This short survey will help us better understand how the QAF is being used, how helpful it has been in supporting your work, and what can be done to improve it. Your input will contribute directly to future updates of both the framework and the related tools. You do not need to provide any personal information.

Thank you for helping us strengthen Open Science training through better tools and shared practices!

[Start General Feedback Survey](#)

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2. GENERAL FEEDBACK

S4E Quality Compass

General Feedback survey

About you

1. Which of the following most accurately defines your current experience in developing learning/training materials?

Select your experience

- Select your experience
- I regularly design learning materials
- I occasionally design learning materials
- I regularly give trainings
- I occasionally give trainings
- None of the above

3. How familiar are you with the implementation of FAIR data principles in learning materials?

Not familiar at all Somewhat familiar Very familiar

DOING THE SELF-ASSESSMENT: STEP BY STEP

• Step 1: Start the test

Click Start self-assessment on the self-assessment page to begin answering questions. Each question corresponds to an **indicator** from the QAF.

The screenshot shows the Skills4EOSC Quality Compass app interface. The top navigation bar is blue with the Skills4EOSC logo on the left and a hamburger menu icon followed by 'S4E Quality Compass'. The left sidebar is dark blue and contains links for 'About', 'Quality Self-assessment Test', 'General Feedback', 'Terms of Service', and 'Privacy Policy'. The main content area is orange and features the heading 'Self-assessment test'. Below the heading, there is a paragraph explaining the test's scope and a paragraph about the report generated after submission. A large blue button labeled 'Start Self-assessment Test' is centered at the bottom of the main content area. The footer contains copyright information, logos for Skills4EOSC, EOSC, the European Union, UC3M, and Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Skills4EOSC S4E Quality Compass

Self-assessment test

The Skills4EOSC Quality self-assessment test covers all indicators from the Skills4EOSC Quality Assurance Framework. During the test, you will navigate through 5 sections: Background Information, Content and Structure, Implementation, Evaluation and Licensing and Ethics. In addition to answering the questions, we encourage you to provide any comments or doubts you may have about a question. Just click on the flag next to each question, write your comments and send them.

After submitting your answers, you will get a report on your course compliance with our quality framework. This report provides your scores by section and by subframework and recommendations on how to improve your learning materials.

Regarding personal data collection, you don't need to provide any personal information you don't wish to be stored. You will still receive your report and results regardless of providing personal information. Any information you decide to provide together with your answers and feedback will be stored for research purposes and to keep improving the tool. For more information about this, visit our Privacy Policy page in the sidebar menu

[Start Self-assessment Test](#)

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- **Step 2: Answer each indicator by section**

Each question is Yes/No. Answer honestly based on your course. If you are unsure, use the help text provided within each question. A progress bar updates automatically as you proceed.

The screenshot displays the Skills4EOSC Quality Compass app interface. At the top, the app title "S4E Quality Compass" is visible. Below it, the main heading "S4E Quality Self-assessment" is centered. A progress bar shows five stages: "Background Information", "Content & Structure", "Implementation", "Evaluation", and "Licensing & Ethics". The "Licensing & Ethics" stage is highlighted in pink, indicating the current section. A progress indicator shows "4%" completion. Below the progress bar, the section title "Licensing & Ethics" is displayed. A pink header bar reads "Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)". Underneath, there is a "Feedback" icon (a red flag) and a "Help note" icon (a blue question mark). A "Note" pop-up box is overlaid on the screen, containing the text: "In addition to informing about the applicable licence, the resource should also indicate who holds the IP rights (e.g. by including the phrase 'all rights are with the respective authors')." Below the note, a question is partially visible: "... who is its intellectual property (IP) rights holder?".

- **Step 3: Leave feedback if needed**

Still uncertain? You can click the **flag icon** to leave a comment or suggest improvements to the question or its notes – your input helps improve the tool for everyone.

By clicking on send feedback, the flag icon will turn red and your feedback will be stored together with your answers. You can edit your feedback at any time by clicking the icon again and submitting an updated version.

Licensing & Ethics

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

Feedback

Help notes

Question

1. Does the resource identify who is its intellectual property (IP) rights holder?

Yes

No

- **Step 4: Submit**

Once you've completed the self-assessment, click **Submit** to view your results.

[Previous](#)[Submit](#)

What You Get After Submission

Once submitted, the app generates a personalized **Results Panel** showing:

- Your course level of maturity

Your Course Quality Report

Your course maturity level

Level 3

Level 3 – Managed — Full minimal compliance + learning resource reviews.

- Your total number of **Minimal** and **Detailed** indicators fulfilled

Your score

[Total score](#)[Score by section](#)[Score by sub-framework](#)

34 / 51

Total Yes Answers

28 / 28

Minimal Level - Yes Answers

6 / 23

Detailed Level - Yes Answers

- A visual breakdown by section and sub-framework

- A visualisation of all your responses:

- Downloadable tips and best practices for areas where you scored "No" or left questions unanswered

How Can You Improve the Quality of Your Course?					
<input type="button" value="Copy"/> <input type="button" value="CSV"/> <input type="button" value="Excel"/> <input type="button" value="PDF"/> <input type="button" value="Print"/>		Search: <input type="text"/>			
Question	Level	Answer	Best Practice	subframework	pages
Does the resource contain, as outlined in the MVS profile , relevant terms selected from Open Science taxonomies or controlled vocabularies in its keywords?	minimal	No	It is suggested to include keywords about the resource. It can include Open Science skills terms outlined in the MVS. The skill set concepts covered by the MVS and suggested to use in the learning resource are identified using the European Skills, Competences and Occupations taxonomy. Other terms can be selected from an Open Science-related taxonomy, ontology or controlled vocabulary (e.g.: t4FS , CSCCE Glossary , FORRT Glossary , Open Science Dictionary , EuroSciVoc).	MVS	1. Content & Structure
Is metadata available to describe the learning resource?	minimal	No answer	The learning resource should be described using a suitable metadata schema that is easily accessible to everyone. It is preferable that the metadata is available in both human and machine readable format.	FAIR	1. Content & Structure
Is the RDA minimal (or domain specific) metadata schema used for the learning resource description?	minimal	No answer	Use a standardised metadata schema such as the RDA minimal metadata schema or domain-specific schemas when describing the learning resource. Both learners and instructors should be able to access all fields defined with the metadata schema.	FAIR	1. Content & Structure
Does the resource have coherently structured content for all elements of the MVS profile in its metadata?	minimal		The learning resource has a coherent structure description of its MVS elements, based on a metadata schema (e.g. RDA minimal metadata for learning resources)	MVS	1. Content & Structure
Is the goal/description of the resource in line with the essential skills and/or main activities listed in the MVS profile for the stated target audience?	minimal	No	The target audience stated should be consistent with the correspondent role/s in this list. The MVS is meant to be used by anyone involved in developing the skills of whichever role is described by that MVS (e.g. including people who are in the same role, and want to plan their own training needs).	MVS	1. Content & Structure

Showing 1 to 5 of 10 entries

Previous 1 2 Next

- A downloadable summary of your records

COLOR CODING:

- **Green:** your “yes” answers (both Minimal and Detailed)
- **Red:** your “No” answers on Minimal indicators – priority for improvement

- **Yellow:** your “No” answers on Detailed indicators – lower priority
- **Grey:** questions not answered.

Your Answers

Copy CSV Excel PDF Print Search:

Question	Framework	Section	Answer	Level	Feedback
Are access rules (authentication & authorisation) implemented for the learning resource?	FAIR	2. Implementation	No	minimal	
If applicable, are all reused resources clearly attributed and compliant with compatible licenses?	FAIR	2. Implementation	Yes	minimal	
Does the resource adopt an open community approach regarding its quality and reachability?	FAIR	2. Implementation	Yes	detailed	
Have you employed a versioning system to track and control changes in your materials?	FAIR	2. Implementation	Yes	detailed	
Does the resource include the date it was published and/or the date of the latest version?	ESSENTIAL	2. Implementation	Yes	minimal	
Does each content or instructional unit end with an activity/assignment that allows for learner feedback?	ESSENTIAL	3. Evaluation	Yes	detailed	
Do the activities and assignments of the resource help the stated target audience to learn any of the essential skills and competences identified in the MVS profile ?	MVS	3. Evaluation	Yes	detailed	
Is the grading policy communicated in a way that clearly defines expectations for the course and its assignments?	ESSENTIAL	3. Evaluation	Yes	detailed	
Does the course offer some kind of certification (badge or micro-credentials)?	ESSENTIAL	3. Evaluation	No	detailed	
Does the available learning resource include the possibility to provide feedback or comments from learners that can be used for improvement?	FAIR	3. Evaluation	Yes	detailed	

Showing 41 to 50 of 60 entries

Previous 1 2 3 4 5 6 Next

WHY IS THIS USEFUL?

- It helps you make your course **clearer, more accessible, and more FAIR**
- It supports **continuous improvement** over time
- It helps you align with shared **S4E project and community practices**
- You can **repeat the self-assessment as many times as you like** — whether you're refining the same course or checking a different one.

Next, we'll look at how the QAF and app are used in practice to support real-world training quality.

3.2 What Happens to Your Answers?

When you complete a self-assessment using the S4E Quality Compass, your answers are stored securely. These responses help us:

- Understand how the QAF is being used
- Improve the app's features and questions
- Identify areas where additional support or clarification is needed
- Strengthen the overall quality assurance framework for the community

You may be asked a few optional questions (e.g.: your role, institution, field of expertise, connection to the S4E project, the title of your course, or your prior experience with QA). These are completely voluntary — you can skip them and still receive your full results and feedback report.

YOUR DATA, YOUR CHOICE

You are free to withdraw your data at any time. If you choose to do so, your records will be permanently deleted from our system.

| PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION (GDPR)

All data collected through the app is handled in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679.

- Your personal data will never be used for commercial purposes.
- All responses are stored securely and used strictly for research, app improvement, and framework development.
- You retain full rights over your data, including the right to access, rectify, or delete it at any time.

For questions or concerns regarding your data, or to request deletion, please contact us at: marinasa@pa.uc3m.es and inaki.ucar@uc3m.es.

| 3.3 In Summary

The QAF and the Quality Compass app:

- Help make Open Science training clearer, more FAIR, and better aligned with community needs
- Are easy to use and designed for everyone – no technical expertise required
- Support real, step-by-step improvements in both content and delivery
- Empower course creators to embed Open Science practices into every part of the learning journey

4. The QAF in Practice: Improving S4E Courses and Learning Platform

The QAF Checklist & Guide and the S4E Quality Compass app are not just tools for ticking boxes — they're designed to support real improvements in how Open Science training is delivered, shared, and maintained across institutions and communities.

4.1. Improving Train-the-Trainer (TtT) Courses

During the Skills4EOSC project, the QAF was used to evaluate and improve several Train-the-Trainer (TtT) courses. Here's how it worked in practice:

- Trainers and course teams used the Checklist & Guide during the early design phase to ensure they were covering the essentials
- Once the courses were drafted, course designers self-assessed their learning resources against the QAF
- T2.4 team members also reviewed the same courses, comparing scores and providing targeted feedback
- Where scores didn't match, questions were clarified, and course materials were updated
- Courses were improved iteratively — making them not just about Open Science, but actual examples of Open Science in practice
- In some cases, course teams ran final self-assessments in the app for further evaluation

This process showed that the QAF can help identify what's missing, misunderstood, or unclear — and guides meaningful revisions, not just formal evaluations.

4.2. Beyond the Course: Improving the Learning Platform

While the main QAF focuses on the course level, it also includes an ELSI expert-oriented extension for those managing learning platforms. This helps ensure that platform features — such as the Privacy Policy and Terms of Service — are also aligned with ethical and legal good practices.

This alignment of the learning platform with the ELSI aspects reinforces the overall integrity and trustworthiness of Open Science training environments.

4.3. Supporting Continuous Improvement

The S4E Quality Compass is designed to support long-term quality development — not just one-time evaluations. It can be used to:

- Review and revise existing materials
- Plan new courses with quality in mind
- Train new staff and share best practices
- Monitor progress over time using maturity levels
- Encourage teams and institutions to gradually move from minimal compliance to detailed, high-quality training practices

5. Conclusions

The S4E Quality Compass app, together with the QAF and supporting tools, provides a simple and effective way to improve the design and delivery of Open Science training. Whether you're starting to build a course or looking to refine an existing one, the framework helps ensure that your learning materials are clear, accessible, ethically sound, and aligned with community standards.

You don't need to be a quality assurance expert to use the QAF — just a trainer or course designer willing to reflect, review, and improve. With easy-to-use tools like the Checklist & Guide and the self-assessment app, the QAF becomes a valuable companion throughout the entire course development process.

More than just a checklist, the QAF encourages continuous learning and quality growth — helping ensure that Open Science training doesn't just teach good practices, but actively embeds them into the way courses are created and shared.

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 Funded by
the European Union

co-funded by
 UK Research
and Innovation

Skills4EOOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140].